

Review

Quantifying and attributing land use-induced carbon emissions to biomass consumption: A critical assessment of existing approaches

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ABSTRACT

Biomass production generates land use impacts in the form of emissions from Forestry and Other Land Use (FOLU), i.e. due to changes in ecosystem carbon stocks. Recently, consumption-based accounting (CBA) approaches have emerged as alternatives to conventional production-based accounts, quantifying FOLU emissions associated with biomass consumption, for example, of particular territories. However, the quantification and allocation of FOLU emissions to individual biomass products, a fundamental part of CBA approaches, is a complex endeavour. Existing studies make diverging methodological choices, which are rarely critically discussed. In this study, we provide a structured overview of existing CBA approaches to estimating FOLU emissions. We cluster the literature in a two-by-two grid, distinguishing the primary element under investigation (impacts of changing consumption patterns in a region vs. impacts of consumption on production landscapes) and the analytical lens (prospective vs retrospective). Further, we identify three distinct dimensions which characterise the way in which different studies allocate FOLU emissions to biomass products: the choice of reference system and the spatial and temporal scales. Finally, we identify three frontiers that require future attention: (1) overcoming structural biases which underestimate FOLU emissions from territories that experienced deforestation in the distant past, (2) explicitly tackling the interdependence of proximate causes and ultimate drivers of land use change, and (3) assessing uncertainties and understanding the effects of land management. In this way, we enable a critical assessment of appropriate methods, support a nuanced interpretation of results from particular approaches as well as enhance the informative value of CBA approaches related to FOLU emissions. Our analysis contributes to discussions on sustainable land use practices with respect to biomass consumption and has implications for informing international climate policy in scenarios where consumption-based approaches are adopted in practice.

1. Introduction

Land use is an important driver of global climate change (Houghton, 2020). Emissions from land use change, denoted as FOLU ('Forestry and Other Land Use') emissions (IPCC, 2019), occur through carbon release or sequestration induced either by land conversion from one land use category to another of different carbon density (e.g. from forestland to cropland) or by land-use intensity changes within a given land-use category (e.g. the conversion of naturally regenerated forests into forest plantations). Global ecosystems currently act as net carbon sources, made up of gross emissions from land-use change (20 GtCO₂/year), only partially offset by forest regrowth (14 GtCO₂/year) (IPCC, 2019).

Agricultural expansion for growing biomass consumption (used as food, material or energy) is the biggest driver of land-use change, and consequently, of FOLU emissions (Curtis et al., 2018). Agricultural production systems may expand into natural ecosystems (De Sy et al., 2019; Pendrill et al., 2019) as well as on land already in use (Baumann et al., 2017). The impact of changes in land-use intensity on ecosystem

carbon stocks are equally important to such land conversions, but remains much less documented (Erb et al., 2018).

Production and consumption have increasingly become spatially disconnected (Erb et al., 2009; Meyfroidt and Lambin, 2011; Qiang et al., 2013). The flows between distant production and consumption systems, and their associated feedbacks, is often denoted as teleconnection or telecoupling (Liu et al., 2013; Friis et al., 2016). This has been highlighted by connections established between centres of production of particular commodities (for example, beef and soy in South America, oil palm in South-East Asia) and global consumption choices (Lee et al., 2014; Cardoso et al., 2016).

In contrast to national greenhouse gas inventories, which follow a consistent territorial, or production-based, approach of emissions accounting, quantifying the effects of consumption on emissions requires consumption-based accounting ('CBA') approaches. CBA approaches attribute emissions to products consumed by or within the system under investigation on the basis of their environmental footprint, irrespective of their place of production (Davis et al., 2014). Such approaches have

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come into prominence due to the globalization of supply chains (Lambin et al., 2018), growth of emissions embodied in trade (Verburg et al., 2009; Xu et al., 2020), concerns about ecologically unequal exchange (Krausmann and Langthaler, 2019) and calls to adopt sustainable consumption practices (Griscom et al., 2017; Roe et al., 2019).

Until recently, CBA approaches quantifying the environmental impact of biomass consumption mainly focussed on calculating 'embodied' land areas (Meyfroidt et al., 2010; Kastner et al., 2014), i.e. the total land areas used for biomass consumed in a specific country, independent of their geographic location (domestic or remote). Differences among these studies originate from methodological choices related to diverging research questions, and have been discussed in detail elsewhere (Bruckner et al., 2015; Schaffartzik et al., 2015; Hubacek and Feng, 2016).

Lately, CBA approaches have been extended to include FOLU emissions (Hansis et al., 2015). To be able to arrive at consistent consumption-based accounts for FOLU emissions, several challenges related to allocating emissions to products and processes need to be addressed. These challenges partly arise due to legacy effects grounded in the 'slow-in, rapid out' nature of carbon stock dynamics (Korner, 2003): FOLU emissions are not only the result of current activities, but also represent recovery dynamics from past disturbances (Davis et al., 2014; Erb et al., 2014). In addition, land use for commodity production implies opportunity costs, i.e. the carbon stock increases that would occur in the absence of land use (Searchinger et al., 2018). The inclusion or exclusion of such opportunity costs is an additional important decision in consumption-based FOLU accounting. These factors have implications for policy and practice, in terms of attributing responsibilities of FOLU emissions to products and territories, accounting for increased emissions coverage and including issues of equity and justice (Goh et al., 2016; Afionis et al., 2017).

In contrast to the vivid discussion around consumption-based accounting of land area demand (Kastner et al., 2014; Schaffartzik et al., 2015), the methodological choices of CBA approaches on FOLU emissions are currently not systematically mapped in the literature. However, the growing policy relevance of the field, as an alternative to conventional production-based accounts (Afionis et al., 2017), necessitates a critical overview of the diversity of approaches which currently exist. Its importance is two-fold: to inform researchers and practitioners about the implications of different methods for interpreting empirical results and to increase comparability across case studies.

In this article, we take stock of different approaches of accounting for FOLU emissions driven by biomass trade and consumption, and establish a framework to classify them. Our objectives are to:

- (1) Identify the conceptual framings and methodological choices in existing CBA approaches to quantify FOLU emissions.
- (2) Assess the socio-ecological processes that CBA approaches capture and the structural biases that emerge from them, to outline future research needs.

2. Methods: focus of literature review

We analysed studies of consumption-based accounting of FOLU emissions, including changes in biomass and soil carbon stocks from land conversion and land-use intensity change. Our aim was to identify and critically discuss methodologies, and to establish typologies by inductively identifying commonalities within a set of cases (Meyfroidt et al., 2018). We did not aim for a full coverage of existing empirical studies but focussed our attention on a comprehensive assessment of different methodological approaches to CBA. This allowed the in-depth exploration of specific research objectives and unaddressed research gaps associated with individual approaches.

We followed a study selection approach starting with studies of consumption-based land use change accounting, some to which several of the co-authors have contributed. Based on reference lists of these

studies and a literature search on Google Scholar (with the terms 'trade', 'biomass', 'emissions', 'consumption', 'land use', 'footprint'), we identified additional studies and stopped once we obtained a good coverage of various methodological approaches to CBA. Thus, the list of assessed studies must not be interpreted as exhaustive list of studies, but rather an empirical basis where all approaches are comprehensively represented by illustrative studies.

We selected studies in our analysis that met the following criteria:

- Application of a methodology designed to provide estimates of FOLU emissions associated with the production of specific agricultural and forestry commodities in a given territory. FOLU emissions may be represented either as total FOLU emissions, FOLU emissions intensities (per unit product) or FOLU emissions per unit area.
- Representation of a large area (regional/global) with significant land-use impacts, or for which imports play an important role in domestic consumption.

In this way, we excluded studies focussed on sectoral-wide approaches, i.e. those not distinguishing individual products (Peters et al., 2011). We found 20 relevant studies that provide explicit estimates of FOLU emissions attributed to the consumption of individual biomass products, or the production of particular commodities (Table 1).

The selected studies included two sub-regional studies focussing on consumption-based FOLU emissions in the Brazilian Amazon, ten studies quantifying FOLU emissions emerging in or resulting from individual countries, three studies on regionally-aggregated groups like the European Union, and five global studies. Studies diverged in terms of temporal scale and accounted for FOLU emissions either as actual emissions (i.e. the difference in ecosystem carbon stocks between two years) or as sequestration potential foregone (i.e. the difference between actual carbon stock change and carbon stock change in the absence of land use, or if vegetation were left for natural succession). Prominent research themes captured in studies included emissions from deforestation in a given spatio-temporal context (Saikku et al., 2012; Pendrill et al., 2019; Rulli et al., 2019), impacts of a particular commodity - for example, beef, soybean and oil palm (Zaks et al., 2009; Karstensen et al., 2013; Aboud et al., 2015; Escobar et al., 2020) and the impact of dietary patterns on agricultural and FOLU emissions (Sandström et al., 2018). The selected studies aimed to represent an overview of existing methodological approaches to attribute FOLU emissions to commodities.

3. Results: objectives and methodological dimensions of consumption-based FOLU emissions accounts

3.1. Prevailing research objectives

Across analysed studies, we find that various research objectives coexist. We developed a two-dimensional grid (Fig. 1) to categorize the studies according to two distinct dimensions. The first dimension represents a difference of topical focus between assessing processes driving land changes (i.e. the description of changing consumption patterns) and their environmental impacts (i.e. the estimation of on-ground FOLU emissions). The second dimension concerns the main focus of the approach, distinguishing the observation of ongoing trends (a 'retrospective' analytical approach) from the analyses of different potential scenarios (a 'prospective' analytical approach). Through these binary categories, we identified four distinct clusters of research objectives (hereafter, Research Clusters). Each cluster is characterized by typical research questions, although diverging methodological approaches could also be discerned within each of these clusters.

Research Cluster I, Impact Accounting (retrospective, focus on ecological impacts), describes FOLU emissions affected in a specific country or region. It makes up the most populated cluster in terms of methodological diversity. This approach focusses on the quantification of FOLU emissions in a given territory from changes in land-use practices

Table 1

The 20 selected studies on CBA approaches to FOLU emissions accounting. Studies are characterized by their topical and geographic setting, temporal coverage and the FOLU emissions metric assessed in individual studies (“FOLU Emissions Indicator”). The metric can be in the form of total emissions (“FOLU emissions”), emissions per unit of area or product (“FOLU emissions footprints/FOLU emissions intensities”) or carbon sequestration potential foregone induced by consumption (“sequestration potential foregone”). See text for more details and *SI Table 2* for the level of spatial aggregation and considered carbon pools for each study.

Reference	Topical and geographic focus	Temporal coverage	FOLU Emissions Indicator
Abood et al. (2015)	Oil palm-driven deforestation in Indonesia	2000–2010	FOLU emissions
Bryngelsson et al. (2016)	Global impacts of consumption changes in the European Union for 30 major commodity groups	Up to 2050	Sequestration potential foregone
Castanheira and Freire (2013)	Soybean-driven land use changes in Brazil and Argentina imported into the European Union	2010	FOLU emissions
Cederberg et al. (2011)	Land use change impacts of beef production in the Brazilian Amazon	1996–2006	FOLU emissions footprints
Escobar et al. (2020)	Embodied emissions in Brazilian soybean exports	2010–2015	FOLU emissions footprints
Flynn et al. (2012)	Land use change emissions associated with oil palm, soybean and oilseed rape for top 20 global producers	2008	FOLU emissions intensities
Henders et al. (2015)	Embodied emissions of beef, soybean, oil palm and wood products from seven producing countries - Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Indonesia, Malaysia, Papua New Guinea and Paraguay	2000–2011	FOLU emissions
Hörtenhuber et al. (2014)	Land use change footprinting for the production of barley (in Austria) and soybean (in Brazil)	1992–2011	FOLU emissions intensities
Karstensen et al. (2013)	Attribution of commodity-driven deforestation from beef and soybean production to consumers in Brazil	1990–2010	FOLU emissions
Lee et al. (2014)	Land use change emissions from oil palm expansion in large-scale and small land holdings in Indonesia	2000–2010	FOLU emissions
Marques et al. (2019)	Global land use impacts in terms of lost carbon sequestration from commodity production for all commodity groups	2000–2011	Sequestration potential foregone
Pendrill et al. (2019)	Attribution of tropical deforestation to international trade for all commodity groups	2010–2014	FOLU emissions

Table 1 (continued)

Reference	Topical and geographic focus	Temporal coverage	FOLU Emissions Indicator
Persson et al. (2014)	Land use change footprinting for beef and soybean (in Brazil) and oil palm production (in Indonesia)	2010	FOLU emissions intensities
Ponsioen and Blonk (2012)	Land use change footprinting for soybean (in Argentina and Brazil) and oil palm (in Indonesia and Malaysia)	2010, based on trend analysis between 1990 and 2009	FOLU emissions expressed as Global Warming Potential from land use changes
Rulli et al. (2019)	Oil palm expansion on commodity land concessions in Indonesia	2000–2015	FOLU emissions induced by consumer countries domestically
Saikku et al. (2012)	Embodied emissions in Brazilian beef and Indonesian palm oil	2007	FOLU emissions embodied in exports
Sandström et al. (2018)	Land use footprinting of biomass consumption in the European Union for all commodity groups	2010	FOLU emissions intensities
Searchinger et al. (2018)	Opportunity costs of land use for commodity consumption in comparison to other land uses	Not specified	Sequestration potential foregone
Verburg et al. (2009)	Land use emissions linked to global agricultural trade liberalization for all commodity groups	Up to 2050	FOLU emissions
Zaks et al. (2009)	Land use change emissions attribution for beef and soybean production in the Brazilian Amazon	1990–2006	FOLU emissions

induced by biomass consumption. Studies describe change patterns of natural ecosystems driven by agricultural expansion, typically focussing on ecosystems at risk from increasing commodity consumption ([Zaks et al., 2009](#); [Flynn et al., 2012](#); [Ponsioen and Blonk, 2012](#); [Saikku et al., 2012](#)). Research in this cluster uses datasets on carbon stocks in natural ecosystems to quantify FOLU emissions induced by land use ([Pendrill et al., 2019](#); [Rulli et al., 2019](#)).

Research Cluster II, Footprint Accounting (retrospective, focus on human drivers), focusses on the environmental burden of consumption levels and trends in important consumer territories, quantifying the embodied FOLU emissions in biomass consumption. Rooted in economic geography and ecological economics ([Meyfroidt et al., 2013](#)), this approach provides evidence of the spatial disconnect existing between production and consumption centres and the role of particular centres of production in global biomass consumption ([Persson et al., 2014](#); [Henders et al., 2015](#)). Together with traditional LCA approaches, the approach demonstrates empirical evidence on current consumption practices and quantifies the impacts of specific consumption patterns, such as dietary choices ([Cederberg et al., 2011](#); [Sandström et al., 2018](#)).

Research Cluster III, What-if Scenario Analysis (prospective, focus on human drivers), offers different options for a given level of consumption and provides a framework for their comparison. The approach demonstrates emissions estimates from different idealized scenarios ([Verburg et al., 2009](#); [Castanheira and Freire, 2013](#)). Analyses in this cluster quantify the FOLU emissions induced by different consumption options or strategies ([Bryngelsson et al., 2016](#)). Such analyses intend to project

Fig. 1. A categorization of studies into research clusters. A two-by-two grid allows the classification of research foci in studies analysing FOLU emissions from CBA approaches. ‘n’ represents the number of assessed studies in each cluster.

how FOLU emissions patterns develop under given scenarios, with the potential to serve as useful tools to support policy and guide actions towards sustainable consumption choices.

Research Cluster IV, Normative Optimization (prospective, focus on ecological impacts), focusses on describing the best possible use of land under given framework conditions. In general, this approach seeks to optimize land use patterns to minimize FOLU emissions under predefined objectives or parameters. It involves evaluating the synergies and trade-offs of production and consumption in terms of their ecological impacts, and the expected emissions from different choices of consumption (Searchinger et al., 2018), thus providing an indication of the optimal use of land required to meet diverging consumption objectives.

3.2. Methodological dimensions characterizing FOLU emissions accounting

Next to research objectives, we identify three major methodological dimensions which determine the basis of quantification and attribution

of FOLU emissions in CBA approaches. These are (1) the choice of reference system and the (2) spatial and (3) temporal resolutions (Fig. 2). The reference system describes the baseline for comparison of carbon stock change from land use, using either existing stocks or carbon stock potentials as a baseline. The spatial resolution distinguishes spatially-aggregated (e.g. national totals) from spatially-explicit approaches, whereas the temporal resolution distinguishes static (focusing on FOLU emissions in one year) from dynamic approaches (considering of non-linear temporal effects across several years).

3.2.1. Reference system

FOLU emissions are the result of changes in carbon stocks in vegetation and soils driven by land conversions (changes in land-use or land-cover types) and land management (changes of ecosystem properties within one land-use type) (Pongratz et al., 2018). In this context, two different reference systems can be chosen in an analysis. One reference system demonstrates changes in existing carbon stocks and associated FOLU emissions, which is assessed by calculating the difference in existing carbon stocks and those that prevailed before the particular land use process (hereafter, ‘actual FOLU emissions’). An alternative reference system refers to the carbon stocks that would potentially exist in the absence of the respective land-use activity (i.e. under natural succession, saturating at the climax carbon stock under potential vegetation). This approach quantifies the opportunity cost of land use (hereafter, ‘sequestration potential foregone’). The two approaches yield different, and at times contrasting, results, making the transparency of the choice and its application essential to derive actionable conclusions (Koponen et al., 2018).

Most studies calculate FOLU emissions following the ‘actual FOLU emissions’ approach, mirroring the approaches established for national greenhouse gas inventories (Grassi et al., 2018). A prominent application is to calculate the loss of forest carbon stocks as a consequence of agricultural expansion. Data sources used for such assessments differ. Some studies use actual carbon stock densities of natural ecosystems from the literature to estimate FOLU emissions from commodity-driven deforestation (Persson et al., 2014; Henders et al., 2015; Pendrill et al., 2019). Other studies rely on standardized factors provided by IPCC-led Tier 1 and Tier 2 approaches (Eggleston et al., 2006) to estimate changes from typical actual carbon stock densities (Flynn et al., 2012; Castanheira and Freire, 2013). For geographically-restricted and place-based analyses, studies use local or regional emission factors, for example, in the case of Brazilian beef and soybean (Karstensen et al., 2013; Hörtenhuber et al., 2014; Escobar et al., 2020) and Indonesian oil palm (Lee et al., 2014; Abood et al., 2015; Rulli et al., 2019).

Studies that follow the sequestration potential foregone approach are less frequent and also rely on various different datasets. The difference between existing carbon stocks of used lands and hypothetical carbon stock dynamics can be quantified on basis of actual forest stocking and

Fig. 2. The methodological dimensions of accounting for FOLU emissions in CBA approaches. The reference system distinguishes between comparisons to actual carbon stocks (C_{act}) across time periods $C(t_2)$ and $C(t_1)$ and sequestration potentials in the absence of land use (C_{pot}). The spatial resolution focusses on the level of aggregation of the approach. The temporal resolution distinguishes between FOLU emissions tracked in a given year (static approach) and non-linear temporal dynamics over several years (dynamic approach). The dotted line represents the tracking of FOLU emissions per unit product across supply chains, which is outside the scope of this study.

regrowth potentials (Bryngelsson et al., 2016) or hypothetical carbon stocking potentials, referring to the stocks that would prevail in the absence of any previous land use but under current environmental conditions (Searchinger et al., 2018; Marques et al., 2019). By quantifying the degree of disturbance of current land use patterns over potential conditions, the opportunity costs imposed by current land uses are assessed. Marques et al. use a carbon stock foregone approach over a short to medium-term timeframe to quantify the sequestration potential of land currently under use (for discussions on temporal characteristics, see below). Searchinger et al. propose the Carbon Opportunity Costs (COC) concept, describing how a given land unit can potentially serve one of several uses. The decision to produce commodities on that unit involves an opportunity cost of preventing its regeneration which, in many cases, would constitute a strong carbon sink. This value judgement forms the bedrock of the optimization approach, which focusses on meeting several objectives (for example, food supply and climate change mitigation), under a given constraint (in this case, land area demand).

3.2.2. Spatial resolution

Studies also differ according to the spatial resolution in quantifying FOLU emissions. Spatially-aggregated approaches describe territory-scale (at the level of municipalities to nations) net totals of land use change. Spatially-explicit approaches, in contrast, depict gross changes at fine spatial resolutions (in the studies analysed, spatial resolutions range from sub-kilometre assessments to coarser assessments at 0.5°) and take the spatial heterogeneity of land-use patterns and dynamics into account.

Aggregate approaches rely on statistical databases like FAOSTAT which provide production and consumption flows at national levels. Analysis at finer administrative scales, which has been a key advancement of initiatives focussing on describing global supply chains like the TRASE database, are also coming into recognition (Escobar et al., 2020; zu Ermgassen et al., 2020; note that the latter was not included in the study because it did not fulfil established criteria for inclusion, but its approach is methodologically similar to the first, which was included). Such databases provide estimates of the net expansion or contraction of commodity production. Hence, they only account for the net area changes of land classes. Commonly, aggregate approaches at national levels are combined with physical trade matrices or multi-regional input output tables and land footprints to determine FOLU emissions associated with biomass consumption (Persson et al., 2014; Henders et al., 2015). Further, region-focussed studies consider aggregated national-level statistics for analysis (Saikku et al., 2012; Karstensen et al., 2013), and FOLU emissions from these territories are further resolved for the biomes from which they may have emerged (Flynn et al., 2012; Ponsioen and Blonk, 2012; Henders et al., 2015).

Spatially-explicit approaches, on the other hand, provide FOLU emissions estimates at fine spatial scales for individual territories where land use associated with biomass consumption has taken place. These approaches are characterized by their ability to take into account local site characteristics and production systems, in addition to using some spatial information available only at aggregated levels (Escobar et al., 2020). Marques et al. for example, use land use maps, corrected for agricultural areas and permanent pastures from existing literature, to map land use dynamics globally and attribute these changes to commodity production regimes. Further, the use of spatially-explicit models (for example, the Spatial Production Allocation Model) helps identify global crop distributions and can be merged with potential vegetation maps to estimate sequestration potentials foregone from commodity production (Searchinger et al., 2018). Land use matrices may also be used to allocate emissions based on pro-rata changes of given land use categories respective to other land uses, or by using rules-based systems, which attempt to characterize the shifting nature of land use after a particular land conversion event. Rules-based systems, for example, set up priority rules to assess post-deforestation land use (cropland/pasture) and allocate FOLU emissions to these land use classes (Pendril et al.,

2019).

These method choices bring into focus the distinction between direct and indirect ways to attribute FOLU emissions to products. Direct allocation requires high resolution spatially-explicit datasets on commodity production, commonly for an assessment of post-deforestation land use. This can be done through concession maps or other locally-detailed spatial information (Lee et al., 2014; Abood et al., 2015; Rulli et al., 2019). However, with spatially-aggregated data, allocation has to be performed in an indirect manner. This can be done on the basis of the share of consumption of consumer countries (Karstensen et al., 2013), emissions within biomes/territories, share of expansion of each crop (Sandström et al., 2018), the crop's carbon opportunity costs (Searchinger et al., 2018), land area used by individual commodities (Saikku et al., 2012) or market revenues (Ponsioen and Blonk, 2012).

3.2.3. Temporal resolution

The attribution of FOLU emissions over time in CBA approaches requires assumptions and choices on temporal time scales and resolutions. This has both conceptual (for example, how many years after land clearing should emissions be allocated to commodities?) and empirical (for example, soil carbon emissions occurring for many years after the land conversion event (Houghton et al., 2012)) bases pertaining to the dynamics of the carbon cycle. We discern static and dynamic approaches to solving this challenge.

Static studies employ a time-step of one year and provide FOLU accounting for a particular production cycle. They demonstrate the impacts of particular strategies and scenarios by taking reference estimates from one particular year to infer FOLU emissions from the extent of consumption-induced land use changes (Flynn et al., 2012; Saikku et al., 2012). Dynamic studies, on the other hand, cover a multi-year period extending, for example, 10 years (Henders et al., 2015; Marques et al., 2019) or 20 years (Karstensen et al., 2013), which could be an outcome of a single land use event, but could also involve the dynamic interaction of multiple land use changes over time on the same land parcel (Baumann et al., 2017).

Both static and dynamic approaches face the challenge of resolving for the 'slow-in, rapid-out' nature of the carbon cycle (Korner, 2003), when projecting current land use changes into the future ('amortization period') and/or accounting for dynamics in the past ('legacy emissions'). The temporal allocation of FOLU emissions is done either linearly over a fixed time period by allocating emissions uniformly (Cederberg et al., 2011; Pendril et al., 2019), or dynamically, by taking gradual saturation effects into account (Zaks et al., 2009; Persson et al., 2014; Henders et al., 2015).

The amortization period refers to the period over which FOLU emissions from land conversion are distributed over production in the years following land conversion, instead of attributing them to the one year in which they emerged. It can legitimately be considered that those FOLU emissions should be distributed among biomass products consumed over the next 5, 10, 20 or even 100 years (Bryngelsson et al., 2016), all benefiting from the initial land cover change (Davis et al., 2014). This period is based on normative judgements of production capacities as well as short and long-term risks. Analysed studies have moved forward different approaches to assign amortization periods because of the sensitivity of the chosen period to emissions estimates. For example, compared to a 50-year amortization period, a 20-year period led to a 400% increase in the FOLU emissions allocated to beef production in a given year in Brazil (Cederberg et al., 2011).

A novel method for considering amortization periods is the economic discount rate approach as a reflection of contemporary climate policy objectives of valuing climate change mitigation over time (Ponsioen and Blonk, 2012; Searchinger et al., 2018). Discount rates typically account for the costs of short and long-term damages as well as the risks of using land for productive activities instead of forest regeneration. Timescales of allocation may also be linked to ecological processes, conforming to the regrowth cycles of forests or the time taken for soil carbon to attain

re-equilibrium after disturbance (Flynn et al., 2012; Bryngelsson et al., 2016).

Land may be utilized for multiple purposes over time. With regard to amortization periods, one important consideration is the distribution between land clearing and future productive activities on the deforested land. FOLU emissions may be distributed according to the type and quantity of commodities produced to show the progression of post-deforestation land use (Pendrell et al., 2019). Land may be cleared using a variety of mechanisms (timber harvest/fire). A fraction of FOLU emissions from land use change can be attributed to these activities (Cederberg et al., 2011; Persson et al., 2014). Cleared land may even remain unused for a few production cycles immediately after clearing (Morton et al., 2008). However, there exists no standard convention on the number of years a converted unit of land is used for biomass production in the future (Searchinger et al., 2018).

In addition, there are also actual empirical long-term emissions to consider. FOLU emissions from changing soil organic carbon stocks, for example, occur over several years after land conversion or changes in land use management (Guo and Gifford, 2002; Murty et al., 2002). While amortization periods help estimate FOLU emissions induced by current changes in land use in dynamic studies, ‘legacy emissions’ from past land use changes remain largely unaccounted for (Davis et al., 2014). These emissions represent the carbon release from slow carbon pools from past land use changes. In addition to the current rates of land conversion in natural ecosystems, which are higher than those at any time in the past (Baccini et al., 2017), legacy emissions further add to observed emissions trajectories. Although one study considers a 13-year legacy emission period from deforested biomass (Karstensen et al., 2013), legacy emissions are found to stretch far beyond this short timescale in carbon cycle modelling studies (Foster et al., 2003; Pongratz et al., 2014).

3.3. Synopsis of conceptual and methodological differences

Fig. 3 demonstrates the methodological pathways of existing accounting approaches and maps individual studies to the identified methodological choices. The Impact Accounting cluster remains the

most populated, followed by the Land Use Footprinting and the What-if clusters. The vast majority of studies (17 out of 20) focused on actual FOLU emissions, often addressing consumption-driven tropical deforestation. Studies of actual FOLU emissions mostly use aggregate national-level analyses, while two of the three sequestration potential foregone studies used spatially-explicit approaches. Among the temporal resolution, multi-year approaches remain the most populated. We found only one approach (the time-agnostic approach by Searchinger et al.) which linked a spatially-explicit spatial resolution with a static temporal resolution. SI Table 1 summarizes the links between Research Clusters and methodological dimensions of individual studies.

4. Discussion: socio-ecological blind spots and research frontiers

The research objectives and methodological choices described above provide insights on some broader conceptual judgements with important implications for specific socio-ecological processes, such as forest transitions, and allow us to map some future research frontiers. We identify three such topics.

4.1. Structural biases in attribution of FOLU emissions

The transformation of natural ecosystems (for example, deforestation, forest degradation or forest management) to meet the demand for biomass commodities is the major process responsible for FOLU emissions. Discussing the effect of changing consumption patterns hence requires a thorough understanding of the implications of various approaches to quantifying FOLU emissions induced by the production of agricultural and forest commodities. We found that a majority of studies use the ‘actual FOLU emissions’ approach, while only a handful focus on ‘sequestration potential foregone’. Quantifying actual FOLU emissions is a suitable approach to study recent deforestation, which is a topic of immediate relevance in the tropics (Baccini et al., 2017) and remains central to debates on how to reduce ongoing deforestation. Actual FOLU emissions embodied in international trade have been successfully

Fig. 3. Methodological path for investigating FOLU emissions in CBA approaches. Numbers represent the studies under each pathway. Colours represent methodological paths adopted by one or several studies, initiated by the Research Cluster. Red: Impact Accounting, Green: Normative Optimization; Dark Blue: Land Use Footprinting; Yellow: What-if Scenario Analysis. For details on pathways adopted by individual studies, see SI Table 1. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

quantified to unravel the emissions impact of outsourcing deforestation from industrialized temperate countries to tropical countries (Henders et al., 2015; Pendrill et al., 2019). However, effects of deforestation or forest degradation prior to the period of analysis, i.e. “land-use legacies” (Erb et al., 2013; Thom et al., 2018), remain unaccounted for. For instance, in cases where past land uses have depleted carbon stocks before the chosen study period, current FOLU emissions can be zero or even negative despite growing harvest volumes i.e. forests acting as net carbon sinks. In such cases, the actual emission approach does not attribute FOLU emissions to the harvest activity; rather it could potentially even attribute a sink to biomass products (Kastner et al., 2011).

In contrast, the sequestration potential foregone approach, i.e. the comparison of current carbon stock dynamics with hypothetical carbon stock dynamics in the absence of land use (Searchinger et al., 2018; Marques et al., 2019), enables attribution of FOLU emissions to products irrespective of the current direction of FOLU emissions (positive or negative). This approach is suited to assess the FOLU emission impacts both in contexts of deforestation and forest recovery as well as in contexts where ecosystems act as carbon sinks as a consequence of recovery from degradation in the distant past, as is the case in many industrialized countries (Gingrich et al., 2007; Mather, 2007; Magerl et al., 2019). Accounting for the sink foregone has the benefit of demonstrating landscape reforestation potentials (Brancalion et al., 2019) and thus quantifying the sequestration potentials of the spatial optimization of land use at the global scale.

It is important to note that the sequestration potential foregone approach is less developed conceptually and empirically than the accounting of actual FOLU emissions. Large uncertainties prevail regarding maximum carbon sequestration potentials and foregone sinks cannot readily be added to emissions from other activities (such as agricultural production) because it represents a hypothetical, and not a physical, flow. When focussing exclusively on fluxes, the approach is also not able to quantify emissions from ongoing deforestation processes, e.g. in the tropics, because the approach mobilizes stocks; the impact on flows (such as NPP, or Net Ecosystem Production) might be much lower and negligible in the context of emission accounting.

We observe an over-representation of actual FOLU emissions accounting approaches, which hides emissions impacts induced in countries where deforestation and forest degradation happened in the distant past and which are now net exporters of deforestation (Henders et al., 2015), that might result in biased interpretations. The magnitude of the difference between quantifying FOLU emissions using these two approaches remains, as yet, unquantified. While both approaches have their benefits and limitations and are complementary in nature, if applied in conjunction, they would be able to reveal a more comprehensive picture of FOLU emissions across different geographic contexts.

4.2. Proximate causes and ultimate drivers of FOLU emissions

The choice of spatial resolution implicates a tacit decision between the analysis of proximate causes and ultimate drivers of land use change (Geist and Lambin, 2002). Proximate causes represent direct human actions and immediate pressures that are associated with actual land use change in a particular area, while ultimate drivers indicate underlying social processes which may happen at higher scales or distant places (Geist and Lambin, 2002; Meyfroidt et al., 2018). Applying spatially-explicit approaches render analyses closer to assessments of proximate causes, since quantifying gross land use changes is apt to describe the role of individual land-use types. In contrast, aggregated approaches are closer to analyses of ultimate drivers, such as the change in demand for cropland, irrespective of where exactly it is cultivated.

Increasing methodological effort has been put into assessing FOLU emissions using spatially-explicit approaches. This has helped reveal the geographic distribution of agricultural expansion in high detail and improved reliability in FOLU emissions accounting, by taking subnational heterogeneities into account. Trade-offs resulting from

consumption demands and commonly-agreed societal objectives (for example, climate mitigation targets) can be resolved at this scale (Searchinger et al., 2018). Recent computational developments have enabled the extension of spatially-explicit data to global scales (Curtis et al., 2018; Searchinger et al., 2018). Additionally, the availability of locally-relevant spatial information, for example, the geographical distribution of land concessions (Schönweger et al., 2012; Abood et al., 2015; Escobar et al., 2020) is further expected to enhance their capability for policy action.

However, spatially-explicit approaches are unable to account for the underlying causes (policy change, behaviour shifts, economic outcomes) of commodity trade and consumption. This makes these approaches vulnerable to over-simplification of land use change, whereas in reality commodity-based land use change accounting is a complex mix of drivers, causes and feedbacks (Friis et al., 2016).

We therefore argue that a careful selection of spatial resolution is required to answer specific research questions. National-scale trends are important for understanding policy implications of existing processes; sub-national trends, such as changes urban consumer preferences, may be important drivers of change and require subnational analyses, while supra-national scales may be relevant to address the role of multinational companies and international trade agreements. In this context, aligning the spatial level of analysis with research objectives and data availability while taking into account interactions across multiple scales continues to be a crucial methodological and analytical challenge (Liu, 2017; Gardner et al., 2019).

4.3. Land management effects on FOLU emissions

Existing approaches capture only the most straightforward impacts of land use on natural ecosystems, based on spatial information on previously existing vegetation and subsequent land use. Despite evidence of its direct and overwhelming impacts on carbon stocks (Erb et al., 2018), land management practices remain overlooked in analyses. The presence of crop-level as well as regional-level yield differences, the loss, recovery and accumulation of soil organic carbon, existing phenological differences and the relationship of carbon fluxes with forest age classes (Pongratz et al., 2018) can significantly impact FOLU emissions estimates, but are inadequately addressed. Carbon stocks of managed lands outside forests are usually assumed to be negligible. This means that FOLU emissions from managed lands are fixed at artificially low values.

At the landscape level, uncertainties based on the reliability of spatial information in complex landscapes persist among approaches. It is important to note that estimates on the extent of certain land use types, for example, grazing lands, pastures and forests, are based on hard-to-define land classifications and thresholds. Land cover information from spatially-explicit models, on the other hand, often rely on process-based modelling approaches, whose estimations do not always match field measurements or national inventories (Erb et al., 2007; Ciais et al., 2008; Grassi et al., 2018). These sources of uncertainty are often not focussed on explicitly, which may be leading to a consistent underestimation of FOLU emissions (Arneeth et al., 2017). In addition, the accounting implications of successive land use changes (for example, deforestation to pasture to cropland on the same land parcel), a dynamic previously identified in some regions (Baumann et al., 2017), remains currently under-explored.

In this context, we argue that with enhanced data availability and process understanding, future research with an explicit focus on land management practices can further demonstrate how FOLU emissions are realised in practice. For example, advancements in datasets on crop species selection, tillage practices, grazing practices and forest management will support an enhanced understanding and estimation of changes in carbon stocks related to land use intensity (Erb et al., 2017).

5. Concluding remarks

The estimation and attribution of FOLU emissions embodied in trade and consumption remains a key research and policy frontier. Our study contributes towards efforts to contextualize its methodologies and suggests pathways for methodological advancements in the future. Future research that considers the methodological judgements, biases and research frontiers that we identify can provide further critical insights into consumption-based FOLU emissions accounting. To this end, different accounting approaches should be seen as complementary, providing options to choose appropriate approaches that can answer the questions at hand.

From a policy perspective, consumption-based approaches identify emissions-intensive trade flows and key leverage points to focus interventions, with implications for climate mitigation targets in developed as well as emerging economies. Such approaches are likely to be increasingly adopted in practice as robust tools to inform climate action and decision-making. For example, these approaches could potentially monitor initiatives under the EU's upcoming actions on reducing deforestation in its supply chains (Bager et al., 2020). In this background, our review is aimed to provide a platform for comparison and interpretation of different consumption-based accounting approaches for FOLU emissions.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112228>.

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